

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

No6
MAXSUS SON

BAKALAVR TALABALARINIG MAQOLALARI TO'PLAMI

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

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Elektron nashr. 256 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil mayda ruxsat etildi.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 28-fevraldagi 333/5-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

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INTRODUCTION

Profitability plays a crucial role in assessing the efficiency of an enterprise. It is one of the most significant indicators reflecting the financial condition, profit potential, and the efficient use of resources. The main goal of economic analysis is to evaluate the enterprise's performance and determine its development prospects.

Profitability indicators have a special significance in this process, as they make it possible to measure the operational, financial, and investment efficiency of the enterprise. Each profitability indicator is unique and demonstrates how the enterprise carries out its activities. For instance, indicators such as return on assets, return on capital, and return on sales influence not only the financial condition of the enterprise but also its strategic decision-making.

The calculation and analysis of profitability within enterprise management constitute a key factor in the decision-making process, thereby contributing to the efficient allocation of resources and enhancing economic stability. In this context, a comprehensive analysis of profitability indicators is essential for ensuring the long-term development of the enterprise.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Profitability indicators are widely regarded as some of the most important financial and economic metrics in assessing the efficiency of enterprise performance. These indicators allow for the evaluation of an enterprise's profit-generating capacity, efficiency in resource utilization, and financial stability. Various authors have approached this subject through different theoretical lenses and have analyzed profitability from multiple perspectives.

For example, V.V. Kovalev, in his work "Financial Analysis: A Systematic Approach to Managerial Decision-Making", considers profitability to be the key outcome of enterprise activity. According to him, profitability is a comprehensive indicator that reflects the overall performance of an enterprise's production, financial, and commercial operations, and it serves as a fundamental factor in shaping strategic directions. Kovalev emphasizes that in analyzing profitability indicators, it is necessary to study their components separately—namely, net profit, revenues, expenses, and asset dynamics.

On the other hand, M.D. Yudanov (2019) views profitability not merely as a measure of profit, but as a multifaceted concept that is interconnected with risk levels, capital structure, and external factors. He argues that financial indicators, including profitability, are directly influenced by the external economic environment, and that macroeconomic conditions, the degree of competition, and price volatility must also be taken into account when evaluating them.

Uzbek authors have also conducted a number of practical studies in this area. For instance, Sh. Juraev and N. Khamroqulov (2021), in their analysis of small and medium-sized enterprises operating in Uzbekistan, used statistical methods to examine the relationship between profitability indicators and efficiency levels. In their recommendations, they emphasized the need for a comprehensive analysis based on return on equity (ROE), return on assets (ROA), and return on sales (ROS) indicators.

Their analysis revealed that although net profits in enterprises are increasing, imbalances in the cost structure are causing a decline in profitability levels. This situation underscores the need to evaluate not only profit figures but also the quality of expenditures in the analysis.

In international literature, particularly in the book "Fundamentals of Financial Management" by R. Brigham and J. Houston (2021), the impact of profitability indicators on a company's overall financial strategy is examined in depth. The authors thoroughly explain how these indicators provide valuable information for investors, creditors, and management in the decision-making process. According to them, the most crucial factors in determining company value are return on assets and return on shareholders' equity. They especially consider profitability to be a key financial indicator in building competitive advantage.

Additionally, D. Norqulov (2022), in his article, warns that profitability indicators may be misinterpreted in practice. He notes that while many enterprises report year-on-year increases in profitability, this growth does not always reflect improved efficiency. It may be the result of artificial income generation or deferred expenses. Therefore, he recommends that profitability be analyzed in conjunction with other financial indicators such as liquidity, solvency, and cash flows.

Overall, the literature review shows that although profitability indicators are powerful tools in evaluating an enterprise's financial condition, correct interpretation and integration with other factors are essential. Profitability is not merely a numerical indicator — it is a complex concept closely tied to strategic decisions, management mechanisms, and the external economic environment. For this reason, in order to thoroughly assess enterprise efficiency, profitability analysis must be approached through a systematic and analytical lens.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study utilizes a mixed-methods approach combining theoretical analysis with empirical evaluation to examine the role of profitability indicators in assessing enterprise performance. The research is grounded in a review of both classical and modern economic literature, where key concepts such as Net Profit Margin (NPM), Return on Assets (ROA), and Return on Equity (ROE) are studied through the works of scholars like V.V. Kovalev, A.Ya. Yudanov, and international authors such as Brigham and Houston. As an empirical basis, the case of “Samarqand Meva Export” LLC—an enterprise engaged in freezing, packaging, and exporting fruits to Russia and Europe—was selected due to the availability of financial data for 2022–2023 and its relevance to export-oriented business models. Quantitative data were obtained from the company’s financial reports and included variables such as revenue, net profit, total assets, and equity. These values were used to calculate profitability indicators using standard formulas, with all data expressed in UZS to enable comparative analysis. The study applied basic descriptive and ratio analysis techniques to assess changes in profitability and financial performance over time, while also considering internal cost structures and external factors such as exchange rate stability. Though the findings provide valuable insight, the research is limited by its focus on a single enterprise over two years. All data were collected ethically, ensuring transparency and confidentiality throughout the research process.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In this study, the practical significance of profitability indicators in evaluating enterprise efficiency was analyzed using the case of “Samarqand Meva Export” LLC, based on data from 2022 and 2023. This company is engaged in freezing, packaging, and exporting fruits to Russia and European countries. Three main profitability indicators were selected for the analysis: Net Profit Margin (NPM), Return on Assets (ROA), and Return on Equity (ROE).

Net Profit Margin (NPM)	Return on Assets (ROA)	Return on Equity (ROE)
Formula: $NPM = (\text{Net Profit} / \text{Revenue}) \times 100$	Formula: $ROA = (\text{Net Profit} / \text{Total Assets}) \times 100$	Formula: $ROE = (\text{Net Profit} / \text{Equity}) \times 100$

Net Profit Margin (NPM)

Name of Indicator	2022	2023
Revenue	11.8 billion UZS	11.8 billion UZS
Net Profit	945 million UZS	1,210 million UZS
Net Profit Margin	8.0%	9.2%

In 2023, revenue increased by 11.8%, while net profit grew by 28%. This growth in profitability can be attributed to optimized expenses, reduced production costs, and the stabilization of foreign currency income from exports.

Return on Assets (ROA)

Name of Indicator	2022	2023
Total Assets	10.4 billion UZS	12.1 billion UZS
ROE	9.1%	10.0%

Despite the company’s total assets increasing by 1.7 billion UZS, the net profit generated from these assets also grew. This indicates that the investments were allocated effectively and that the asset turnover rate remained strong.

Return on Equity (ROE)

Name of Indicator	2022	2023
Equity	6.1 billion UZS	6.7 billion UZS
ROE	15.5%	18.1%

The significant increase in the ROE level is a positive sign for shareholders and investors. It indicates that the company is generating a high return on its equity.

Based on the above empirical analysis, it can be concluded that “Samarqand Meva Export” LLC significantly improved its financial stability, profit-generating capacity, and efficiency in resource utilization in 2023. The steady growth in profitability indicators reflects sound management decisions, strengthened cost control, and a strategic approach adapted to market demands. Therefore, profitability analysis serves not only as a financial tool but also as a guiding compass in management.

Profitability indicators play a key role in assessing enterprise efficiency. They help evaluate the company's financial performance, the effectiveness of management decisions, investment potential, and the level of resource utilization. The conducted empirical analysis shows that profitability indicators reflect not only the volume of financial profit but also the quality of management. This highlights the necessity of using profitability as a core tool in evaluating performance and forming management strategies.

The increase in profitability levels indicates that the company has managed to balance its growing revenues with its cost base. However, to ensure long-term efficiency, the following key recommendations should be considered:

1. Conduct profitability analysis using a comprehensive approach

Rather than relying on just one or two indicators, a comparative analysis should be carried out using Net Profit Margin, Return on Assets, Return on Equity, Return on Investment, and Product Profitability. This will provide a more complete and realistic picture of the company's situation.

2. Analyze and optimize the cost structure

The empirical analysis demonstrated that costs have a direct impact on profitability. Therefore, each type of expense should be studied separately, and unnecessary or inefficient expenditures should be reduced to improve profitability.

3. Analyze profitability by business segment

If the company operates in multiple areas, separate profitability indicators should be calculated for each. This helps identify which segments generate the most profit.

4. Conduct financial analysis in a dynamic, time-based format

Profitability should be analyzed not only annually but also quarterly or monthly. This allows seasonal changes, price fluctuations, and shifts in demand to be tracked, enabling timely management responses.

5. Direct investments toward high-return and high-profitability areas

As seen from the high ROA and ROE figures, when assets are used effectively, overall profit also increases. Therefore, investments should be focused on assets that offer high returns.

6. Develop strategic decisions based on analysis results

Financial analysis enables company leadership to critically assess their operations and revise strategic plans. For example, the production of low-profit products may be reduced in favor of focusing on more profitable areas.

7. Implement methodologies aligned with international standards

Using analysis methods based on International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) ensures transparency in assessing profitability — not only for internal evaluations but also for external investors.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Profitability indicators serve as a key criterion in assessing the economic efficiency of enterprise performance. Based on the theoretical and empirical analysis presented in this article, it can be observed that the level of profitability not only reflects a company's ability to generate profit but also indicates the effectiveness of its management system, the culture of resource utilization, and the soundness of strategic decisions.

The conducted analysis reveals that profitability indicators are interrelated, and by applying a comprehensive approach to their analysis, it becomes possible to draw accurate conclusions regarding the company's financial condition and its changes under the influence of internal and external factors. In particular, indicators such as net profit margin, return on assets, and return on equity demonstrate the relationship between revenue and expenses, the company's ability to utilize its assets, and the effectiveness of using its own capital.

Moreover, the empirical analysis has shown that improvements in profitability are directly linked to cost control, enhanced product quality, efficient resource allocation, and well-founded investment decisions. From this perspective, profitability analysis is not merely a tool for preparing reports but serves as a reliable foundation for shaping the strategic development plans of a company.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that any enterprise can ensure its financial stability, strengthen its competitiveness, and move toward long-term success by consistently analyzing its performance, evaluating profitability, and identifying the factors that influence it.

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IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

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"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>